

Efficient and Safe Disposal of Unused or Expired Medicines

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Abstract

Medicines known as the lifeline of human and animal health have a vital role in curing various ailments. The giant Indian pharmaceutical firm is known for its production potential and is the largest provider of generic drugs globally. Despite such a huge production, the Indian public still does not get adequate medicines at reasonable cost commonly known as a form of health inequality, and is attributed to various reasons. On the contrary, a huge pile of unused or expired medicine is there in every household. This pile-up can create a problem in two ways- one being accidental exposure leading to the risk of various types, sometimes death; the other being the burden on the environment and other living creatures due to improper disposal of drugs to a great extent. In Indian context, there is a lack of awareness amongst the public regarding both safe, efficacious use and disposal of medicines with disposal of medicines in household trash being the most prevalent method. Pertaining to this, the problem of side effects and the emergence of antibiotic resistance are also of great concern. The purpose of the current article is to impart a piece of knowledge, a positive attitude, and practices for the safe disposal of medicines, to raise awareness amongst the common people, and request government officials, policymakers, and health care professionals to provide training to inform and direct the general population on safe and effective disposal techniques for expired or unused pharmaceuticals. This will reduce environmental impact and the problem of antimicrobial resistance to some extent.

Introduction

The Indian pharmaceutical company is the third-biggest by volume in the world and the 14th-largest by value. It is also the world's largest supplier of generic medications. (Annual report, 2021-22, Department of Pharmaceuticals, GOI). Despite a giant producer at one end, there is unequal availability of medicines to a growing population (Raut and Lawale, 2022). Medicines are an important part of human and animal life that are necessary for the treatment of infectious and non-infectious diseases but they must be used with caution. Any unused portion of the medication must be properly disposed to avoid the risk of getting exposed and associated consequences. we came across leftover medicines in every home either in

unused or expired form. Production of huge amounts of medicines to satisfy unmet drug needs, cessation of therapy just after initial recovery, frequently changing health care provider with medicines, lack of proper medical record, and expiry of medicines are some of the reasons responsible for their pile up and it can be anywhere in bathrooms, kitchens, bedrooms, purses, and anywhere we store medicines (FDA.gov). This is further supported by the fact that a much greater portion of drugs is inappropriately prescribed and sold (Who.int), favoring their pile up and wastage thereby further deepening medicinal health inequalities (Raut and Lawale, 2022).

All this reflects the unawareness of the general public, and medical practitioners, and the information gap between the safe, effective use and disposal of medicines. In the Indian context, the problem of improper disposal was found both in the general public as well as in medical practitioners as reported by Zalpuri et al., 2022; Kaur and Bansal, 2021). This poses a serious problem that poses a threat to humans, animals, the environment, and ecosystems altogether (Zuccato et al., 2004; Vollmer, 2010).

Frankly speaking, unused medicines can create a RISK, if they are taken by someone they were not prescribed for; can cause HARM, if accidentally taken by a child or pet and/ or cause DANGER, or even death, if not used as directed. All this raises the question of why put your family at risk? These facts are further supported by examples like the extinction of vultures in South East Asia due to exposure to Diclofenac, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that causes renal failure and death in vultures. The extinction of vultures led to a ban on the use of diclofenac by the government of India, Pakistan, and Nepal in 2006 (Nambirajan et al., 2018). Banning is not a pure alternative as it does not prevent entry of chemicals in ecosystem, other alternatives like safe and effective disposal of drugs are quite important.

Being a pharmaceutical hub, there exists huge responsibility on the nation to dispose of medical and pharmaceutical waste generated at the level of hospitals, consumer doorsteps, retailers, and wholesale drug dealers. All this warrants the safe disposal of unused or expired medicines before they can do harm. Although in this regard, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has issued some guidelines for the proper disposal of unused or expired medicines but still, people in India are not aware of it. (FDA.gov). This article tries to highlight proper disposal methods issued by the food and drug administration (FDA) to reduce the risk burden on humans, the environment, and other ecological species.

FDA guidelines for disposal of unused or expired medicine

The FDA recommends that healthcare providers should inform about the proper disposal of the concerned medicines after their use to all patients. If the above information is not available following steps will help and the same is depicted in Figures 1 and 2 respectively.

1. Disposing at a drug take-back location: It is the best way of disposal and includes locations, sites, or a programme where you can drop your unused medicines including prescribed medicines and medicines without prescription called as over the counter drugs.

Unfortunately, in India, there does not purely exist drug take-back locations but various initiative of various state governments like the PROUD initiative (programme on removal of unused drugs) of Kerala (toi.indiatimes.com); prescription for change initiative in Bangalore (ensydeindia.org); Drug Disposal Awareness Program (DDAP) under Foundation for Health and Environment Research (pharmatutor.org) were working in this field. Besides this, a Covid-19 driven initiative to collect unused medicines was started in Mumbai, Maharashtra (Mumbai.citizenmatters.in). Another approach that can be followed is through proper purchase from and return of medicines to the same store.

2. Flush medicines down the toilet: Remember, not to flush your medicine unless it is in the flush list (FDA.GOV). The drug list contains substances that have the potential to be abused and/or misused and that can result in death from one dose if inappropriately taken. Serious consequences including death may occur if anyone including children, adults, or pets gets accidentally exposed to or used a medicine in the flush list. A variety of medicines containing various active pharmaceutical agents like Fentanyl, Morphine, Buprenorphine, Naloxone Hydrochloride, Acetaminophen, and Aspirin are on the FDA flush list of drugs. The details of various drugs on the flush list can be accessed at <https://www.fda.gov/media/85219/download>. At the same time, the impact of flushing medicines on the environment and water quality were assessed by the FDA thereby assuring the negligible risk to the environment, and in line with this, regular risk assessment was carried out by FDA and regulatory bodies.

3. Disposal in the trash: You can dispose of most medicines in your household trash if the above two options i.e, absence of take-back sites, locations, or programs, and when the medication guide or package insert does not include specific disposal instructions (e.g. flushing). In India, this is the most widely prevalent method of drug disposal conducted mostly in an improper way in almost every household. For efficacious disposal via trash method, one can follow the following steps.

- i) Mix the medicine (liquid or pill) with an unpleasant substance such as cat litter, dirt, garbage, or used coffee grounds. Please do not crush the tablet or capsule.
- ii) Seal the mixture in a plastic bag or in the appropriate container.
- iii) Discard the container in the trash at home.
- iv) Erase all personal information from the prescription label on the empty medicine bottle or box, then discard or recycle the empty medicine bottle or box.

Figure 1 and 2: Effective Disposal Options for Unused or expired Medicines (taken from <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/disposal-unused-medicines-what-you-should-know/drug-disposal-dispose-non-flush-list-medicine-trash>)

Conclusion

Medicines being vital for maintaining health, needs to be properly taken and disposed of after their pile up and/or expiry. Proper disposal of medicines can reduce the overall risk of getting exposed and thereafter associated risks if exposed, to the individuals and the environment. Although various initiatives for the safe disposal of medicines have been launched over the past few years, most people in India are not aware of them. Considering this, we as an individual, medical practitioners need to spread this message in every nook of society and can advise the government and other bodies for the safe disposal of medicines across the country. This may help to augment ongoing environmental degradation, and the problem of anti-microbial resistance, and reduce overall consequences arising due to exposure to unused or expired medicines.

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